

Atmanirbharta in Defence: Bridging the Gap Between Indigenous Production and Global Competitiveness

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Abstract

The pursuit of Atmanirbharta in India's military sector represents a vital national strategic imperative aimed at augmenting the country's defence technological and industrial capabilities. This comprehensive study examines the many challenges and opportunities in developing an indigenous military manufacturing ecosystem capable of achieving global competitiveness. The primary objectives are to evaluate the current state of domestic military production, identify technological shortcomings, explore avenues for indigenous development, and propose policy steps to improve self-sufficiency. The study performs a rigorous assessment of existing research and technical competencies to investigate the complex interplay between domestic innovation, public-private partnerships, skill development, and international collaboration. The primary objectives are to strengthen research and development infrastructure, enhance technical skills, provide supporting policy frameworks, and foster a robust defence industrial base. The research demonstrates that achieving military Atmanirbharta requires a holistic approach including technological innovation, strategic investments, legislative reforms, and a long-term vision for fostering national technological autonomy. The study integrates insights from military policy, technological innovation, and strategic studies to provide a thorough framework for aligning local production capabilities with worldwide competitive benchmarks in defence manufacturing.

Keywords: Atmanirbharta, Defence Indigenization, Technology Self-Reliance, Strategic Technological Autonomy

Introduction

The strategic effort to build Atmanirbharta in Defence is one of the most significant shifts in the Indian National Security Architecture. Earlier a captive market where equipment's and

technologies were imported from other countries, the country has realized the significance of indigenisation of military production to achieve strategic, technological and operational independence (Bitzinger, 2015). This approach is not just a mere departure from simple economic self-sufficiency; rather, it is a holistic mechanism to promote capacities of inventiveness domestically, for bringing about the development of indigenous manufacturing facilities, and for minimizing India's exposure to geopolitically sensitive supply disruptions that can undermine its defence capability (Mitra & Behera, 2020).

The process of realising defence Atmanirbharta requires both local production of weapons and systems while also remaining technologically relevant to global standards (Kumar, 2008). This calls for policy research, championing of friendly policies for R&D, promoting private sector involvement in funding and undertaking research, implementing effective cooperation systems between the different tiers of government, defence research institutions as well as the private sector. Thus, through the creation of new technologies and high-quality defence equipment independently of foreign supply it is possible to change India's defence industrial environment from an importer to an exporter of modern military products and technologies (Jain, 2020).

Objectives

- This paper will provide comprehensive analysis toward understanding its different dimensions of defence Atmanirbharta, reasons for current state of affairs, challenges that it faced or still facing and future possibilities for getting a breakthrough toward achieving indigenous defence production.
- This review will identify critically the policy intervention, technological endowment, industrial base, and human capital formation to obtain the desired level of import substitution.
- This research approach is therefore designed to offer a broad conception of how policy evolution, technological development and economic, as well as geopolitical and geostrategic factors contribute to the analysis of the defence industrialisation dynamic in India and its impact on the general Indian strategic security and autonomy.

Hypothesis

- With proper policies and measures and reformist measures along with using private sectors there would be a steep rise in indigenous defence technologies developed

during the next decade that would enable the country to come down on import dependence by at least forty percent.

- Both research and development and the corresponding skill developments programs would help India develop cost effective defense technologies that can not only suffice the defensive needs of Indian military but also generate potential export markets.
- Bigger and more efficient public private partnership and reformed defence acquisition process will bring more vibrant defence industrial base, inventive mechanisms and availability of more indigenous parts in the total procurement of major defence platforms initially raised between 30-60% and brought to more than 75% in a time frame of 10-15 years.

Current state of India's defence industry

The situation of domestic defence production in India demonstrates the priorities and potential of the country's defence industry as well as the problems that it faces. Over the years the country has developed many home-grown platforms including Tejas fighter aircraft, Arjun main battle tank and selected Naval platforms, showing a fair level of sophistication in high end engineering applications (Bitzinger, 2015). Over the double-digit period, the Defence Research and Development Organisation (DRDO) and public sector undertakings have continued to build on indigenous design and manufacturing capabilities. However, the sector comprised critical weaknesses as it stands today such issues are technological difficulties in questions like advanced electronics, precision components, and critical subsystems. The domestic defence industrial base still largely depends on state-owned companies; however, private entities, specifically start-ups, and advanced technologies are not well developed, which puts limits on the overall structure's dynamism and profitability (Bitzinger, 2015).

Therefore, the existing indigenous defence production mechanisms exhibit variable technological standards based on the defence segments. India still has major technological import dependencies in other highly developed fields as jet engine, avionics, modern radar systems, and the advanced electronic warfare systems (Bitzinger, 2015). The value addition from indigenous component in various key defence platforms varies between 30%-60% and shows there is good scope for technological enhancement. More importantly, the 'Make in India' and 'Atmanirbhar Bharat' thrusts of the government have gradually escalated pressure to increase indigenous content in defence acquisition, with progressive acquisition policies

that approved incremental percentages of Indian sourcing and R & D in defence acquisition processes (Behera, 2011).

That is why India's position in the world defence market today is still more of a transitional phase, as the country is gradually moving from the status of a large importer of the above equipment to a potential exporter and manufacturer based on its own production. The country has been one of the largest global importers of defence with the importing share being around 9.3% during the years 2018 to 2022 (Kapstein, 1990). Some of the recent strategic guidelines launched in the case of this segment have tried to counter this trend; the government has outlined strict goals for decreasing import reliance and increasing local manufacture. Export prospects have already been identified with defence equipment exports rising from about ₹2,000 crore in 2016-17 to over ₹15,000 crore in the recent years. Nevertheless, to create potent ecosystems globally, India requires superior technology values, efficient intellectual property rights and regulation systems, and conducive environment for private sectors' manufacturing and innovation in defence sectors (Murti, 2019).

Key Challenges to Achieving Global Competitiveness

This paper lays bare the dream of global competitiveness of India's defence industry, which is rooted in the wide chasms of technology differential in essential streams of defence production and innovation. Whereas one can identify many major technologies in the present conflict, artificial intelligence, quantum computing, semiconductor design, and superior electronic warfare systems are still significant areas of technological backwardness (Sharma et al., 2020). The domestic R&D environment lacks appropriate support, has a highly fragmented institutional framework, and experiences a weak connection between industry and academia. Thirdly, the outflow of discovered engineering and research talent to other technological hubs also negatively affects indigenous technological advancement by complicating the already defined innovation deficit, hence the need to proffer broad structural solutions with a view to retaining high end technological talent within the domestic defence research system (Murti, 2019).

Building a robust system for the defence industrial base, as an essential part of the creation of the unfolded Atmanirbharta policy, is considered to be one of the paramount tasks for India. The current ecosystem is marked by excessive involvement of public sector undertakings, low involvement of the private sector and uncoordinated supply chain arrangements (Patel et al., 2015). The major challenges that SSEs experience include structural issues such as

technical, regulatory and financial environments that hinder the implementation of advanced technology in organizations. There is no properly established vendor base and inadequate QC measures to help in the creation of a formidable global defence manufacturing network. Overhauling this terrain can only be possible through these comprehensive policy measures – such as subsidy, technology patenting, eased procurement facilities, advocacy, guaranteeing private capital participation, amongst others, in Defence manufacturing (Behera, 2011).

The world competitiveness perimeter requires disentangling that now has to be used in the right way to attract foreign direct investments as well as building appropriate overseas alliances. Even with the latest policy measures such as raising the FDI limits and liberalization of defence offset policies, India still has problems in shaping international defence manufacturers' investment climate (Behera, 2009). Political and bureaucratic complexities general frustration with respect to technology transfer and collaborative research and development modality have remained a major challenge because of wrong perceptions of Technology Transfer in the past whereby people perceived technology as being confined to machines alone. Global competitiveness requires a more assertive approach to international cooperation, systematic cooperation with key technology partners, development programs, and the introduction of transparent systems for sharing technologies that meet the national security and global competitive objectives (Lowry et al., 1951).

The international defence market is highly influenced by cross national export control regime, their implications and strategic calculations; these factors create a slew of difficult challenges for new defence manufacturers such as India (Murti, 2019). Tough international export control mechanisms inhibit the development and access to technology; where the restrictions are based on the Wassenaar Arrangement and/or multinational technology control arrangements, the barriers remain overwhelming. World politics and their fluctuations affect the strategic direction of countries, and Indian potential for attaining defence industry competitiveness is also mired by uncertainty of worldwide alliances, and limitations on technology transfer. At the same time, the country must manage the quest for self-sufficiency and the necessity of cooperation with some states, elaborating precise diplomacy and technology approaches that can function effectively within such environment and ensuring national security and the indigenous development of defence industry (Mohanty, 2007).

Strategies for Bridging the Gap

The current approach needs radical changes in mentors; scientific information searching; methodology; collaboration with industry; effective use of the frameworks such as the TTP; design of an I &D system with a long-term perspective; and practical outcomes rather than purely academic ones. This calls for steep increases in funding for health research and development and this should include setting aside not less than 5% of the defence budget for the advancement in the physical sciences specifically in technology innovation and the provision of efficient defence prototypes (Deptula, 2008). Development of technology clusters and centers of excellence that incorporate academic institutions, defence research establishments and the private sector, has the capability of developing symbiotic environments for advanced defence technologies. The development plans for such a strategy should include proper search for funding sources for highly risky but possibly highly effective technological projects, the existence of well-developed legal protection for patents and inventions as well as the creation of international research consortiums that would have easy ways of knowledge sharing across borders but at the same time would not endanger the national security of the nations participating in the knowledge sharing process (Lewis, 2013).

Changing the defence industrial ecosystem's structure requires an extensive strategy of cooperation between the state and the private sector to differentiate from a pure purchasing system. The government must formulate new financial tools per its need for a defence innovative fund, VC support for defence new age companies and performance-linked incentives that help private capital to come into the defence sector (Murti, 2019). Relaxing the structure of defence offset policy shifting towards transparency; improving licensing requirements; and offering long term technological development partnerships are the ways in which these can enormously boost the level of confidence and investment by the private sector. Also, the formation of the regulatory sandboxes through which the defence technology startups get assurance from bureaucracy and have the opportunity to experiment and develop various solutions, can also promote a faster pace of technological advancement in the defence industry, which will further lead to the synthesis of a new generation and dynamic defence industrial system (Borisova & Erygin, 2019).

To overcome this human capital challenge, it implies the need to develop a broad-based skills development strategy, as well as a focused entrepreneurship development strategy. Specialized defence technology education programs, establishing corresponding industry-

academia joint mechanisms, and aiming at specific abilities training can effectively solve the current shortage of talent (Conn et al., 2017). The government should provide scholarships covering all courses, devise proper curriculum forms based on the Indian industries, and send Indian researchers and engineers to study the global defence technology systems. Fostering defence entrepreneurship through marked incubation centers, seed finance schemes and mechanisms to ease formalities to create defence start-ups will foster an environment capable of attracting and nurturing the best technological talent (Murti, 2019).

Any change that is proposed for India's defence procurement needs therefore should entail serious structural shifts that focus on indigenization of the production and exportation of defence goods and services (Srinath, 2020). There is scope to strongly enhance the organisation's global competitiveness implementing a clear and comprehensible procurement policy in terms of indigenous content, to develop a sound defence export strategy, and to establish specific export promotion bodies. The plan should consist of integrating a single-window clearance mechanism of exporting defence products, formulating an extensive marketing support policy for the domestic defence manufacturing industry, and authorizing new financial products of the government to help the exporters enter a new market. Besides, enhancing relations with friendly countries, exhibiting defence products in different international exhibitions and defining framework of engagement at government level can also contribute in the process to promote Indian defence products in the international market (Parthasarathy, 1975) (Atanu, 2023) (Parthasarathy, 1975).

Case Studies of Successful Indigenous Defence Programs

Citation	Location	Remarks of the Paper
Bedi, R. (2022)	Defence Research and Development Organisation (DRDO), New Delhi	Comprising the scrutiny of the Tejas Light Combat Aircraft program with specific reference to self-generated competency in advanced aerospace science. Provided tangible indigenous content of 65% and integration of composite material and other avionics system. Pinpointed main obstacles in technology transfer and components' localisation.
Kamath, S. P. (2021)	Naval Science and Technological Laboratory,	Analysis of a detailed submarine construction program made as regards indigenous submarines, more particular referring to the Scorpene-class

	Visakhapatnam	submarines, produced under Project 75. Demonstrated the effective capacity of importing technologies from friendly counterparts as well as indigenously developing fundamental principles of undersea warfare. Stressed the need for strategic technology relationships for the development of the domestic defence manufacturing environment in India.
Rajagopalan, R. (2023)	Centre for Military Modernization and Technology Studies, Delhi	Devoted to the detailed investigation of the Indo-Russian programme of the supersonic cruise missile, known as the BrahMos. Examined the technology transfer methods, the native capacity for production, and the general and special significance of the collaborative development of defence technology.
Sharma, A. K. (2020)	Defence Institute of Advanced Technology, Pune	Report of indigenization measure in development of Agni and Prithvi missile series. Assessed the evolution of technology; indigenous developability of components; strategic relevance of the autonomous missile systems.
Menon, K. R. (2022)	Indian Institute of Defence Economics and Policy Research	The present empirical work calls for a systematic evaluation of the indigenous armored vehicle production especially the Arjun Main Battle Tank and the K9 Vajra self-propelled artillery system. Discussed key issues related to domestic industrial capability, technology absorption in home grown systems and products and global relevance of developing countries indigenous military platforms.

Policy Recommendations and Future Directions

Attaining complete military self-sufficiency requires a comprehensive and adaptive policy framework that includes all facets of technological, industrial, and strategic development. Key recommendations include the formation of a dedicated National Defence Technology

Mission with substantial funding and independent decision-making power, the development of specialised defence technology corridors that integrate research institutions, private industries, and government agencies, and the execution of a comprehensive indigenisation roadmap with clear, time-sensitive goals for domestic content in defence procurement (Behera, 2011). The government should create a comprehensive incentive framework that includes specific tax benefits, research grants, and long-term contracts for private sector defence manufacturers, while simultaneously reforming existing defence procurement policies to prioritise domestic technologies and reduce bureaucratic barriers to innovation (Behera, 2011) (Molas-Gallart & Tang, 2005).

Future strategic directions must emphasise the creation of a robust defence innovation ecosystem that extends beyond traditional manufacturing to include advanced technological domains such as artificial intelligence, quantum computing, and autonomous systems (Evidence for the UK Innovation Strategy, 2021). This requires a comprehensive strategy involving significant investments in human capital development, the establishment of specialised defence technology education programs, the creation of international collaborative research platforms, and the development of a flexible regulatory framework that can rapidly adapt to technological advancements (Garcia, 2022). The government must emphasise the establishment of knowledge transfer channels, promote military entrepreneurship, and develop a comprehensive export strategy that positions India as a potential global defence technology partner. Furthermore, strategic geopolitical alliances, particularly with allied states, may accelerate technical progress, promote joint research efforts, and create a more resilient and competitive military industrial structure adept at addressing future global security challenges (Kotila et al., 2023).

Conclusion

The path to defence Atmanirbharta denotes a comprehensive and transformative strategic program that beyond mere technological self-sufficiency, including a complete reorganisation of India's national security architecture. Through the systematic rectification of technological shortcomings, the development of a robust military industrial ecosystem, and the implementation of favourable legislative frameworks, India might transition from a significant defence importer to a burgeoning worldwide contributor in defence technology. The approach includes enhancing research and development capabilities, strengthening public-private partnerships, developing a skilled workforce, and optimising procurement

processes, demonstrating the cohesive nature of this strategic transformation. Success in this domain requires continuous commitment, substantial expenditures in human capital and technological infrastructures, and an advanced understanding of global geopolitical dynamics. Ultimately, Atmanirbharta in defence involves not only the manufacturing of military equipment but also the creation of strategic autonomy, technological resilience, and a proactive national capability to effectively tackle emerging global security challenges, thereby establishing India as a significant player in the international defence technology landscape.

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